

UBD SBE يو.بي.دي. ايس.بي.اي.
UBD SCHOOL OF BUSINESS AND ECONOMICS

UNIVERSITI BRUNEI DARUSSALAM

BB-2208 HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

INDIVIDUAL ASSIGNMENT 2: CASE STUDY ANALYSIS

S&R AQUAFARM - THE FOMBRUN MODEL

Name & Registration Number: Siti Haziqah Binti Haji Juffri (19b8540)

Tutorial Group: Thursday 950AM - 1040AM

Lecturer: Pg Dr Siti Rozaidah Binti Pg Hj Idris

Submission date: November 11th, 2020

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. ABSTRACT	2
2. INTRODUCTION	3
3. PROBLEM STATEMENT	4
4. CASE ANALYSIS - FOMBRUN MODEL	4
4.1. Selection	5
4.2. Appraisal	5
4.3. Rewards	6
4.4. Human Resource Development (Training and Development)	6
5. ALTERNATIVE SOLUTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	7
5.1. Selection	7
5.2. Appraisal	8
5.3. Rewards	9
5.4. Human Resource Development (Training & Development)	10
6. CONCLUSION	10
References	11

ABSTRACT

This case study will explore on the S&R Aquafarm that uses the modern farming technique of Aquaponics which is considered to be more sustainable as the plants and fish can grow symbiotically. The company recently expanded its market by providing supplies of their products to local establishments and supermarkets. However, there are some problems such as lack of experience, limited scale of operation and maintenance cost. This case study will provide solutions to the problems by using the Fombrun Model where there are four phases which are selection, appraisal, rewards and development. These phases mainly target the employees and company on the areas they can improve on in order to resolve the problems. By following the phases accordingly it can help achieve organisational effectiveness and improve their survival rate in the aquaponics industry.

INTRODUCTION

Aquaponics is a farming method that combines both aquaculture (breeding of aquatic animals) with hydroponics (growing of plants in water). This method is considered to be a sustainable organic crop production due to the reliance between the crops and fishes. The waste produced by the fish will be converted into nutrients (that acts as the fertiliser) for the crops to grow while in return, the crops clean the water for the fish. Therefore, the use of fertilisers to grow crops is eliminated with the use of aquaponics and this can be considered as more cost efficient. In comparing aquaponics with the conventional farming method, some argued that aquaponics is better as it is considered to be more organic due to the absence of chemical pesticides in the production of the crops.

S&R Aquafarm is a company in Brunei Darussalam that has practiced the aquaponics method since the early 2011. Previously, the company was known as S&R Aquaculture where they only focused on breeding fish but due to its high cost in maintenance the company eventually adapted the aquaponics method after much research. As a result, the company is able to expand its source of income with the production of fish and vegetables instead of depending on one source only. In addition, the company is able to grow different varieties of plants such as herbs, microgreens and other crops which are sold for home use, distributed to supermarkets and restaurants.

Although aquaponics has its benefits, there are also drawbacks to the method. In relation to the experience by S&R Aquafarm, some of its challenges are high maintenance cost due to fungal and pest infestation, limited variety of crops grown which leads to limited production and market, if an individual does not have an agricultural background it requires an extensive amount of research so that the environment of the system is maintained well. There are studies where HR practices helped in achieving organisational effectiveness (Alrawi, Mohammed, Castilo, Fadlalla, 2017). In this case study, the Fombrun model or Michigan model of HRM (Human Resource Management) will be used to analyse the case and provide possible solutions to the challenges faced by the company.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

In analysing the case of S&R Aquafarm it was understood that there were some problems faced by the company. First, the founders had no knowledge and experience in agriculture and aquaponics which resulted in them having to do extensive research. Second, the scale of operation is small therefore limiting the company's market and quantity of production and requiring them to be selective in what to produce. Lastly, maintenance of the aquaponics system is costly as problems such as pest infestation and fungus often occur. Hence, the Fombrun model is used to provide solutions to these problems.

CASE ANALYSIS - FOMBRUN MODEL

The Fombrun Model of HRM (1984)

The Fombrun model is also known as Michigan School of HRM. It is considered to be a Hard HRM approach where human resource strategies have the best fit to the strategies of the business. For instance, the employees are recruited selectively or they are trained to perform specific tasks. This approach is understood as a strategic process as it is utilising an organisation's human resource effectively given that the HR policies fit with the organisation's business strategy. In this model, it emphasises on how the four key HRM activities which are selection, appraisal, rewards and development contribute to organisational effectiveness.

i. Selection

In discussing the selection phase of the Fombrun model it is understood that the selection of employees is one of the important aspects of hiring new recruits in helping an organisation achieve its goals. This model believes in the process of matching the right people to the right job.

As S&R Aquafarm continues to expand, they will need to hire more people to help maintain the company's production while achieving its goals. Therefore, they have to be selective in their hiring process and hire recruits that match well with the needs of the job. Due to the founders' lack of experience and knowledge in aquaculture and agriculture it has led to certain problems which they eventually overcame but this could have been avoided had they possessed certain knowledge and experience. Therefore, if the company decides to continue growing then these mistakes should be avoided as the consequence of it may delay the company from achieving its desired goals.

Moreover, from the case study it is understood that the aquaponics system requires maintenance to avoid fungal problems and pest infestation. Without the proper maintenance, the products of the company are considered to not be up to the standards or of quality products. The cost of assembling & maintaining the aquaponics system itself is already costly therefore having the right employee is crucial so the systems are well maintained.

ii. Appraisal

Appraisal is understood to be the act of assessing someone. Therefore, the appraisal phase of the Fombrun model is related to the assessment of an employee's performance. This is another important phase as organisations can deduce whether an employee is making contributions in achieving the business' objectives or not. From this it is understood that appraisal plays a role in the development of a company by improving employee's performance so that business objectives can be achieved.

Appraisal in employees should be done occasionally. This is to ensure that the employee's performance is up to the company's standard. Another benefit in conducting appraisals is that the S&R Aquafarm can identify areas that need further improvement. Thus contributing to the

aspects of development of a company. If appraisals on employees are not performed then it may lower a company's quality of production and overall decrease an organisation's effectiveness.

However, appraisal is not limited for the employees of an organisation only. It can also be done on the company as a whole. Due to the development of S&R Aquafarm, the quality of their products must be maintained in order to retain customers. Especially since they are expanding their product supply market from domestic use only to also supplying local cafes, restaurants and also supermarkets. If they do not maintain the quality, they may lose customers and this will affect their income drastically. Moreover, it will also affect the relationship and reputation of the companies or businesses they associate with.

iii. Rewards

In hard hrn it is believed that employees are motivated by salary or other types of compensation. Therefore, by rewarding employees with high pay it can motivate them to work more efficiently and achieve the organisation's objectives.

One of S&R Aquafarm's goals is to grow the company. Therefore, having highly motivated employees is important as they are the responsible in achieving the goals. A method in motivating employees is by rewarding them either by offering a high pay or other compensation or incentives such as bonus pay.

If an organisation does not continue to reward their employee, overtime it may cause the employees to feel demotivated and as a result lower down the company's production level. This can be a problem as it will decrease the company's life span or surviving rate in an industry.

iv. Human Resource Development (Training and Development)

Final phase in the Fombrun model is Human Resource Development or also known as Training and Development. In this phase as the name suggests is the training of employees. By training employees it can bring a lot of benefits to a business.

As S&R Aquafarm can still be considered as new in Brunei Darussalam, training is still an essential aspect for a company just like any other businesses regardless of whether they are a newly established company or not. One of S&R Aquafarm's earlier challenges is that they had

little to no knowledge or experience in the agriculture and aquaponics industry. However, the company was able to overcome this challenge through training.

If training is not provided, the company and its employees will not be able to develop. This is a problem as other competitors may use this as an advantage to provide a more developed product compared to S&R Aquafarm's products. Moreover, buyers or consumers of their products would lose interest in their products if there are no developments seen in the company's product. In addition to that, the employee performance of the company may decrease and as a result lowering the organisation's effectiveness

Therefore, it is important for the company to tackle the problems faced in the company by referring to the Fombrun Model as it can aid in achieving organisational effectiveness as well as develop the company and its employees overtime.

ALTERNATIVE SOLUTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

i. Selection

S&R Aquafarm needs to be selective in the types of recruits they plan to hire. Before hiring employees, they need to assess the areas they are lacking in and investigate what they need. From there they can conclude what are the criterias needed for the job as hard hrn models believe in matching people to jobs or in other words, hiring people based on the job's needs.

A method of selection is by conducting interviews on the interested applicants before they are hired. By conducting interviews, the company will be able to deduce whether the individual is fit for the job and whether they are able to contribute to the company's objectives, goals, and vision. If interviews are not conducted, this can be a problem as the company may face a problem where the employees are incompetent. Over time, this will be a problem as it is creating losses to the company. Therefore, to avoid such problems it is important for a company to conduct interviews prior to hiring new employees.

Another method of selection is by conducting employment tests where the individual is given a standardized test designed to measure skills, intellect or other characteristics then from this test it will provide a certain score or category. An example of this test is aptitude test where it measures

an individual's ability to learn new things. By providing this test, an organisation is able to assess whether the recruit will add contribution to the business and succeed in the job they applied for. Moreover, this test can provide more information regarding how the recruit's cognitive process works compared to interviews. In addition to that, interviews may not provide all the information needed as there are some criterias that are unseen such as understanding a person's cognitive process. If a company does not provide employment tests, it may create problems in the future as they were not able to fully understand how the applicants behave.

Therefore, if S&R Aquafarm applies selection methods in hiring their employees such as by conducting interviews and employment tests, they will be able to deduce whether the applicants are fit for the job or not. Moreover, it will save them from undergoing losses due to hiring the wrong people. In addition, by hiring the right people they can increase the organisation's effectiveness.

ii. Appraisal

Appraisal is essentially a review of an employee's performance and contribution in an organisation. After the process of hiring employees to fill in vacancies, a company should provide appraisals for the employees' performance. By doing this it can help the employees to be aware and improve the areas they are weak in which as a result will also improve an organisation's effectiveness or productivity.

S&R Aquafarm should have appraisals where the employees are assessed by credible organisations or specialists in the aquaponics industry. By doing so, the advice given to them is useful in improving their performance as well as the company's production.

An example of appraisal is 360-degree feedback assessment which includes input of feedback from an individual, their supervisor, and their peers. By doing this type of appraisal, an employee is able to understand how they are perceived and what are their strengths and weaknesses based on the feedback from everyone in the workplace. If appraisals are not conducted in an organisation, it can be a problem as there is no motivation for an employee to develop themselves to be a better employee. Other than that, it does not contribute in achieving the company's goals and objectives.

As stated in the case study, S&R Aquafarm receives advice from the Agricultural Department this can be a method of appraisal on the company overall whether their products are considered to be of good quality or otherwise. Moreover, by receiving feedback from an expert regarding their products, S&R Aquafarm can strive to improve their weaknesses so they can be of the same level as other Aquaponic businesses.

Therefore, S&R Aquafarm should give appraisal to their employees so they can improve their weaknesses in hopes that it can help boost the company's productivity level and the company as well should receive appraisals regarding their products occasionally. By having good quality products and high level of employee performance it can help in boosting S&R Aquafarm's reputation as a business thus making them a strong competitor in the aquaponics industry.

iii. Rewards

As believed by Hard HRM models, rewards are considered as a motivation for employees. An example of rewards is in the form of pay. By providing a higher pay it will motivate employees to work harder. When an employee works harder or efficiently, they will help boost the company's production level. This will help in achieving the company's goal at a faster rate.

An example of rewards is extrinsic rewards where employees are given rewards that are essentially monetary value or in the forms of perks and benefits. S&R Aquafarm can offer their employees a higher pay according to their performance. By doing this, it can help motivate employees to work better and more efficiently so they are able to gain extra pay. Another reward may be in the forms of perks and benefits where the company can provide their employees with valuable perks such as discounts on the company's product. By doing this, it can help promote the company's products to the employees' family and relatives.

If a company does not provide rewards for their employees, it can result in a high number of dissatisfaction in the employees for the company as they do not have the motivation to work. This is a problem as it will increase the level of employee turnover in the company and eventually contribute to the level of unemployment.

Hence, it is important for S&R Aquafarm to provide rewards to their employees as a sign of gratitude or acknowledgement for the hard work to achieve the company's goals.

iv. Human Resource Development (Training & Development)

Training is an important part of the Fombrun Model. There are a few types of training such as induction, on-the-job, and off-the-job. By conducting training on employees it can bring benefits to the company.

As S&R Aquafarm plans to grow, training is an important aspect to help achieve this goal. An example of training is induction whereby new employees are introduced to what are their responsibilities and how to perform their job well. This is crucial as it can help prevent future mishaps considering how expensive it is to set up an aquaponic system. Moreover, induction training helps the employee to familiarise themselves to their surroundings and socialise with their colleagues.

Another example of training is off-the-job where the training is conducted away from their workplace. For instance, the founders of S&R Aquafarm visited a local small aquaponics system to learn about the production. S&R Aquafarm should continue with this method as it helps the employees to understand how to perform their job and increase production level. Moreover, as maintenance is costly it is important that training is given to the employees so they are able to handle and combat pest and fungal problems that often occur in aquaponics systems.

Therefore, training is important for employees as it helps them to understand what they are expected to do and how to perform their job well so they are able to increase the organisation's effectiveness.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, S&R Aquafarm can adapt the Fombrun Model as a method to resolve the company's problem by being selective of their employees, providing appraisals and rewards to keep the employees motivated as well as conducting training so the employees are able to develop themselves. By following all of this, it can contribute to the organisation's productiveness and tackle the problems currently faced by the company.

References

- Alrawi, H. M., Mohammed, S. A., Castillo Jr, F. G., & Fadlalla, S. E. M. EFFECTIVENESS OF HR PRACTICES AT FUJAIRAH MUNICIPALITY: USING THE MICHIGAN MODEL OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT. *European Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 71. Retrieved from http://ppublishing.org/upload/iblock/032/Layout_EJH-5_2017.pdf#page=71
- Hard HRM. (n.d.). Retrieved from http://www.hrsguide.co.uk/introduction_to_hrm/hard-hrm.htm
- Kadiresan, V., Selamat, M. H., Selladurai, S., Ramendran, C. S., & Mohamed, R. K. M. H. (2015). Performance appraisal and training and development of human resource management practices (HRM) on organizational commitment and turnover intention. *Asian Social Science*, 11(24), 162. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Vimala_Kadiresan/publication/282586487_Performance_Appraisal_and_Training_and_Development_of_Human_Resource_Management_Practices_HRM_on_Organizational_Commitment_and_Turnover_Intention/links/56132b2c08aea9fb51c28cb3/Performance-Appraisal-and-Training-and-Development-of-Human-Resource-Management-Practices-HRM-on-Organizational-Commitment-and-Turnover-Intention.pdf
- Musa, S. F. P. D. H., Pg Hj Idris, P. S. R., & Basir, K. H. (2020). *Inspiring Agripreneurs of Brunei*. UNISSA Press, Universiti Islam Sultan Sharif Ali.
- Singh, C. M. (2015). Models of Human Resource Management/Development Practices and its Relevance in Higher Education Institutions. *International Journal of Innovations in Engineering and Management*, 4(2), 16-23. Retrieved from <http://www.academia.edu/download/44500669/IJEM42032015.pdf>